

Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science services - CORBEL -

Deliverable D6.6

Ocean Sampling Day: a demonstrator of a cross-domain distributed data set

WP6 – Data access, management and integration

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Executive Summary

This work addresses the establishment of cross-domain data sets as exemplified by the Ocean Sampling Day. To fulfil this goal a workflow based on the broker service of GFBio to concurrently submit molecular (sequence) data and environmental data to ENA and PANGAEA, by conserving the dependency of the two datasets. With this standard compliant workflow, incremental submissions of large-scale datasets can be easily handled and sustainable cross-linking between two internationally known, long-term repositories were established.

Project objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following objectives described in Work Package 6 Description of Work:

- a) Deliver sustainable, robust and extensible identification resolution and conversion services supporting data management, deposition, discovery and provenance.
- b) Deliver the semantic infrastructure supporting cross-domain use of data identifiers, minimal data standards, data types, tools, and domains required by BMS ESRIs.
- c) Improve interoperability with European e-infrastructures and leverage existing investments these capacities within the biomedical and life science domain.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background

The Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) was established by the EU project Micro B3 as a simultaneous microbial sampling and sequencing campaign of the world's oceans, with the aim to generate the largest standardized microbial data set including a rich set of environmental data in a single day which can serve as a reference data set for generations of experiments to follow in the coming decade [1]. The first OSD events took place on the summer solstice (June 21st) between 2014 and 2016. These cumulative samples, related in time, space and environmental parameters, provide insights into fundamental rules describing microbial diversity and function and contribute to the blue economy through the identification of novel, ocean-derived biotechnologies. In 2017 OSD was continued by the Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR) in Crete as a collaborative yearly event to monitor microbial diversity over time. It is part of the Genomic Observatories Network¹ to help preserve Earth's life support systems and promote sustainable development through a better understanding of the human-environment interaction. OSD creates cross-domain, distributed data sets working with several infrastructures across the world including ELIXIR (ENA, an ELIXIR Core Data Resource and Deposition Database operated by EMBL-EBI and the BioData center of ELIXIR Germany), EMBRC (all nodes participated, with at least France and Belgium also delivering digital infrastructure) and MIRRI (Jacobs University).

Key aspects of OSD

- Centralized logistics and data management, incl. sample handling, sequencing and initial quality control

¹ <http://www.genomicobservatories.org/>

- Publishing OSD data open-access as soon as the data is ready for scientific analysis
- Follows established (meta-)data standards, specifically the M2B3 checklist [2] and the MIxS checklists² [3].
- Links the distributed OSD data across domains and infrastructures, i.e. for example data items in ENA have links to the appropriate data in PANGAEA, the Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science³ and vice versa.

The German Federation for Biological Data (GFBio)⁴ is a network of experts and infrastructures, offering a portfolio of services for research data management in the fields of Biodiversity, Ecology and Environmental Science, including:

- Support for the preparation of Data Management Plans
- Data brokerage, consisting of submission, archiving and publication of data to one of its associated data centers
- An integrated (meta-)data search across the data centers with direct access to a dedicated Visualization and Analysis Tool
- A Terminology Service for managing ontologies and vocabularies, needed for the standardized data description.

The GFBio Data Submission/Brokerage service offers a single point of entry for archiving and publishing complex datasets into one or more of the GFBio data centers⁵. The key features of the service include manual curation of the (meta-) data to meet with appropriate community standards (e.g. MIxS or ABCD) and depositing different data types into appropriate archives with subsequent interlinking via persistent identifiers, like DOIs. The service has been operational for the past 5 years. So far, approximately 900 data sets were archived by GFBio and have already been cited over 1300 times. The service has a dedicated workflow for molecular sequence data, which was developed by experts involved in the data management and publication of the initial OSD events. Sequence data is deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (operated by EMBL-EBI), with metadata standardized according to the Minimum Information About Any Sequence (MIxS). Accompanying environmental measurements are deposited in PANGAEA Data Publisher for Earth and Environmental Science⁶.

As part of the GFBio sustainability concept, a non-profit association (GFBio e.V.) was founded in 2016 and currently has more than 15 institutional members, including universities and research institutions from various biological fields⁷. To ensure the long-term operability of its services, GFBio e.V. together with other key institutions across Germany has applied for funding to establish a National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)⁸ for Biodiversity (NFDI4Biodiversity)⁹.

Description of Work

In 2017 the EMBC infrastructure received funding through the Assemble+ project to continue and sustain OSD with the coordination assigned to the Hellenic Center for Marine Research HCMR in Crete. Following the recommendation of the CORBEL Deliverable 6.1 to "Encourage establishment of

² <https://gensc.org/mixs/>

³ www.pangaea.de

⁴ www.gfbio.org

⁵ www.gfbio.org/data-centers

⁶ www.pangaea.de

⁷ www.gfbio-ev.de

⁸ www.nfdi.de

⁹ www.nfdi4biodiversity.org

data submission brokers who take the responsibility to offer users, in need of complex distributed submissions, a single entry point and take over the responsibility of managing distributed submissions to resources in different domains.", a collaboration with the German Federation for Biological Data (GFBio) was established.

Assemble+ (EMBRC) has successfully organized two Ocean Sampling Events in 2018¹⁰ and 2019¹¹. Data brokerage experts from GFBio attended all relevant Assemble+ workshops and General Assembly meetings and have contributed experience from the initial OSD events. Together with the OSD coordination team from HCMR, the data management of Assemble+ (VLIZ), and ENA, a dedicated workflow for data archival and publication was designed and implemented (Figure 1). The workflow is based on the standard GFBio operating procedure for molecular sequence data with the addition of sample- and meta- data being deposited in OBIS resources for export and availability in even more community standard formats, like Darwin Core. OSD, including this data archiving and publication workflow was presented to relevant working groups of the Genomic Observatories initiative and was deemed a feasible model for sustainable handling of sequence data from coordinated sampling activities. The metagenomic and 16S ribosomal RNA gene (rDNA) amplicon sequencing data from the 2018 event is ready for publication - the metadata was curated by HCMR in close collaboration with experts from GFBio and ENA and standardized according to the M2B3 checklist. The metadata is already submitted to GFBio and the transfer of the data is being organised. The process was partly delayed by the Corona pandemic, so that the final publication of the data will presumably happen after the end of the CORBEL project time. Further data set from the 2018 and 2019 events will follow subsequently. With the sustainability concept of GFBio in place, Assemble+, through the activities of CORBEL Subtask 6.1.1, has secured a sustainable, long-term solution for the incremental publication of the OSD data.

Figure 1. The established workflow of data from OSD to Archives and Analysis. Courtesy of Guy Cochrane (EBI-ENA)

¹⁰ <http://www.assembleplus.eu/research/ocean-sampling-day-2018>

¹¹ <http://www.assembleplus.eu/research/ocean-sampling-day-2019>

Next steps

N/A

References

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2. ten Hoopen, Petra, Stéphane Pesant, Renzo Kottmann, Anna Kopf, Mesude Bicak, Simon Claus, Klaas Deneudt, et al. 2015. Marine microbial biodiversity, bioinformatics and biotechnology (M2B3) data reporting and service standards. Standards in Genomic Sciences 10. ??? 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40793-015-0001-5>.
3. Yilmaz, Pelin, Renzo Kottmann, Dawn Field, Rob Knight, James R Cole, Linda Amaral-Zettler, Jack A Gilbert, et al. 2011. Minimum information about a marker gene sequence (MIMARKS) and minimum information about any (x) sequence (MIxS) specifications. Nature biotechnology 29. Nature Publishing Group, a division of Macmillan Publishers Limited. All Rights Reserved.: 415–20. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt.1823>.

Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed:

No

Adjustments made

None